

A Comparative Study between T Tube Drainage versus Stent in Open CBD Exploration

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Received: 04-11-2024 / Revised: 05-12-2024 / Accepted: 17-12-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Choledocholithiasis refers to the presence of stones within the common bile duct (CBD). The condition can be managed using two principal approaches: endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) or surgical exploration of the CBD. During open CBD exploration, primary closure of the duct is feasible if an intraoperative cholangiogram confirms the absence of residual stones. In the absence of this confirmation or if stones are detected, a stent or T-tube is required to facilitate drainage. This study compared the outcomes of stent placement versus T-tube drainage following open CBD exploration.

Materials and Methods: A total of 78 patients were included in the study. Of these, T-tubes were inserted in 40 patients, while stents were placed in 38 patients. Data analysis was performed to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of the two methods, with particular reference to the study's objectives.

Results: The analysis revealed no significant difference in outcomes between patients managed with T-tube drainage and those treated with stents. Both approaches demonstrated comparable results in terms of post-operative recovery and overall effectiveness in the management of CBD stones.

Conclusion: This study suggests that both T-tube drainage and stents are equally effective options for managing patients undergoing open CBD exploration when primary closure is not feasible. Further research with larger sample sizes may help validate these findings and refine management strategies.

Keywords: Gallstones, Common bile duct, T-tube, Stent.

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Introduction

Common bile duct exploration (CBDE), whether performed via open surgery or laparoscopically, is a vital procedure aimed at managing and preventing a variety of complications such as cholangitis, pancreatitis, and obstructive jaundice, which arise due to the presence of common bile duct stones. Choledocholithiasis, characterized by the formation of stones in the common bile duct, often remains asymptomatic in the early stages, making it a silent disease that can progressively lead to more severe clinical manifestations over time.

Without proper intervention, choledocholithiasis can result in significant morbidity, including recurrent episodes of cholangitis, pancreatitis, and biliary cirrhosis. It has been estimated that approximately 10–20% of individuals with cholelithiasis, or gallstones, will develop choledocholithiasis, highlighting the importance of early detection and management in these patients

[1,2]. Following the surgical removal of stones via CBDE, biliary drainage is a crucial step to ensure the proper resolution of the obstruction and to prevent postoperative complications such as biliary leakage, stricture formation, and recurrent choledocholithiasis. To facilitate drainage, a T-tube or a biliary stent is commonly placed within the common bile duct. The T-tube serves as a drain, allowing bile to flow from the liver into the duodenum while preventing the accumulation of bile in the biliary system, which could lead to complications such as bile leakage or abscess formation. The biliary stent, on the other hand, is often used as an alternative to the T-tube, providing internal biliary drainage and maintaining the patency of the bile duct, thereby preventing stricture formation and reducing the risk of further stone development [3,4].

The practice of T-tube insertion following CBDE was more commonly employed prior to the advent

of endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP), a less invasive procedure that enables the safe and effective internal drainage of the biliary system. ERCP involves the use of a flexible endoscope inserted through the duodenum to access the bile ducts, allowing for the retrieval of stones, the placement of stents, and the management of any other biliary obstructions. ERCP has become the gold standard for biliary drainage in many clinical settings due to its minimally invasive nature and high success rate. However, despite its widespread use in developed countries, ERCP has not been as commonly adopted in developing nations due to limitations in healthcare infrastructure, such as the availability of specialized equipment, trained personnel, and the overall cost of the procedure. This has resulted in continued reliance on T-tube drainage in certain regions, where access to advanced endoscopic techniques is limited [5, 6].

Biliary stents, which can be composed of either plastic or metal, are cylindrical devices commonly used to maintain the patency of the bile duct. These stents help to ensure continuous bile flow, thereby reducing the risk of complications like cholangitis and jaundice. Furthermore, biliary stents can be safely removed through endoscopic procedures, minimizing the risk of complications that might arise from more invasive removal methods. Previous studies examining biliary complications related to T-tube use in both open and laparoscopic surgeries found no significant difference in complication rates. The complications observed were primarily associated with the insertion and removal of the T-tube itself, rather than the surgical technique employed. As a result of these findings, there has been a trend among surgeons towards adopting biliary stenting, which has been associated with better outcomes and fewer complications compared to T-tube drainage [7,8].

Material and Methods

The study was conducted as a prospective investigation. The study population comprised all patients meeting the specified inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria encompassed patients aged 25–65 years of both sexes, those providing informed consent as per the designated pro forma, individuals with radiological evidence of choledocholithiasis, patients indicated for open CBD exploration, and those contraindicated for laparoscopic CBD exploration. Patients younger than 25 or older than 65 years, those unwilling to consent, individuals with multiple comorbidities, and those eligible for ERCP stone retrieval or laparoscopic CBD exploration were excluded.

Detailed clinical histories were obtained, followed by relevant investigations such as blood tests, ultrasound of the abdomen and pelvis, CT scans, and magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) where indicated. Key variables recorded for each patient included age, sex, presenting symptoms, duration of illness, clinical findings, diagnostic results, surgical procedure, and postoperative details.

The patients were randomly divided into two groups. One group underwent T-tube placement, and the other received a stent. A standard open cholecystectomy was performed in both groups. Following a longitudinal choledochotomy, CBD stones were retrieved, and residual stones were cleared using thorough saline irrigation with a feeding tube. In the first group, a 12 Fr T-tube was placed, the CBD defect was closed with 2-0 Vicryl sutures, and the tube was secured to the skin. An abdominal drain was inserted, and the wound was closed in layers. In the second group, a stent was placed, the choledochotomy site was closed with 2-0 Vicryl, and the abdominal drain and wound closure were similarly performed.

Postoperatively, patients in the T-tube group underwent a cholangiogram on the 10th postoperative day, and the T-tube was removed on the 14th day. For the stent group, the stent was removed six weeks postoperatively using ERCP. All patients were monitored for postoperative complications, and their outcomes were recorded during follow-up. The analysis was performed using the chi-square test and Student's paired t-test.

Results

The study consisted of two drainage procedure groups: the T-tube group with 40 patients (51.28%) and the Stent group with 38 patients (48.72%) as shown in Table 1. The clinicodemographic parameters of the two groups are shown in Table 2. The mean age of patients in the T-tube group was 66.3 ± 10.0 years, whereas in the Stent group, it was 76.6 ± 8.6 years. However, the p-value of 0.30 indicates no statistically significant difference between the two groups in terms of age. Similarly, gender distribution was comparable between the groups. In the T-tube group, 17 male patients (42.5%) and 13 female patients (32.5%) were included, while the Stent group had 18 male patients (45%) and 20 female patients (50%). A p-value of 0.12 suggests no significant difference in gender distribution between the two groups. When considering operation time, complications and hospital stay, there was no significant difference between the two groups (Table 2). On comparison of post-operative complications (Table 3), there was no significant difference.

Table 1: No. of patients in study groups

Drainage Procedure	n	%
T-tube	40	51.28
Stenting	38	48.72

Table 2: Clinicodemographic parameters in study groups

Parameter	T-tube (n=40)	Stent (n=38)	p-value
Age	66.3 ± 10.0	76.6 ± 8.6	0.30
Gender; n (%)			
Male	17 (42.50)	18 (45.00)	0.12
Female	13 (32.50)	20 (50.00)	
Operation time (min)	66.2 ± 10.0	76.8 ± 8.6	0.16
Hospital stay (day)	11.9 ± 4.8	10.7 ± 3.7	0.22
Complication; n (%)	3 (7.50)	2 (5.00)	0.06

Table 3: Comparison of post-operative complications

Complications	T-tube	Stent	p-value
Remnant stone	3 (7.50)	4 (10.53)	0.64
Stent Migration	-	6 (15.79)	-
Leakage	1 (2.50)	3 (7.89)	0.28
Peritonitis	1 (2.50)	1 (2.63)	0.98

Discussion

It has been documented that primary repair of the bile duct without bile drainage following endoscopic common bile duct exploration does not show significant differences when compared to the insertion of a T-tube. Nevertheless, T-tube drainage remains widely utilized after such procedures. T-tubes offer benefits such as reducing the risk of intrahepatic abscesses and bile leakage by decompressing the bile duct system. They also allow for post-surgical evaluation of residual stones through cholangiography, which can be removed via biliary endoscopy using the T-tube for irrigation. However, T-tubes present several challenges, including the risk of post-surgical infections, and prolonged maintenance. Due to these issues, various alternative biliary drainage options have been explored, including stent insertion [9,10].

Retrograde stent insertion may significantly lower biliary duct pressure and prevent biliary leakage. Recent studies suggest that retrograde stent insertion following endoscopic choledochotomy and simple repair could serve as an effective alternative to T-tubes [11].

The major advantages of retrograde stent insertion include eliminating the inconvenience of tube maintenance and enabling patients to resume normal activities sooner. However, it is not without drawbacks. If the stent migrates and is removed spontaneously, it may require endoscopic intervention, and stent migration can lead to biliary atresia or cholangitis. Additionally, removing residual stones post-surgery can be difficult. In our study, we encountered three cases where the stent

migrated into the bile duct, necessitating additional endoscopic intervention for removal [12,13].

In our study, there were no significant differences between groups. T-tubes were beneficial for removing residual common bile duct stones but required long-term maintenance (approximately 4 weeks), which was inconvenient for patients. In contrast, patients in the stent group experienced shorter hospitalization and less discomfort. However, if the stent migrated or failed to be removed spontaneously, additional endoscopic procedures were necessary.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that both T-tube drainage and stent placement are equally viable methods for managing patients undergoing open common bile duct (CBD) exploration when primary closure isn't an option. However, additional studies with larger patient populations are needed to confirm these results and enhance future management approaches.

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